

A Molecular Orbital Analysis of the Bonding of Sulphur Monoxide and Sulphur Dioxide towards Rhodium

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CNDO/2 molecular orbital calculations have been performed on the systems *trans*-[Rh(L)Cl(PH₃)₂] (L = SO, SO₂) in order to investigate the nature and energetics of the bonding between rhodium and SO or SO₂ ligand. The computed trends for Rh-S, S-O and Rh-Cl bond strengths, as measured by Wiberg indices and charge distributions suggest that (i) the SO ligand is a better σ -donor and poor π -acceptor than the SO₂ ligand, (ii) the σ - and π -bond fractional Wiberg indices for S-O bond are greater in sulphur monoxide complex than in sulphur dioxide complex and (iii) the SO ligand is a better *trans*-directing ligand. In *trans*-Rh(SO)Cl(PH₃)₂ complex, the highest occupied molecular orbital, $6a''$, is derived from the interactions of $5p_z$ and $4d_{yz}$ orbitals of rhodium with $3\pi^*$ of SO.

Sulphur monoxide is a reactive unstable gas¹. It is evident that SO can be stabilised with transition metal complexes²⁻⁷. The interaction of sulphur monoxide with transition metal systems is still a subject of curiosities. A brief study of Extended Hückel molecular orbital calculations for iridium sulphur monoxide complex has been reported⁸. Herein, I wish to report the electronic structure of the Rh-SO and Rh-SO₂ systems.

Computational details :

Molecular orbital calculations were performed using a CNDO/2-U method⁹. The orbitals $4d$, $5s$ and $5p$ of rhodium were included in the calculations. Wave functions for these orbitals were those given by Burns¹⁰. The wave functions used for S ($3s$ and $3p$), Cl ($3s$ and $3p$), P ($3s$ and $3p$), O ($2s$ and $2p$) and H ($1s$) were Slater type orbitals. The values for the orbital exponent, beta and electronegativities¹¹ are listed in Table 1. Atomic charges and bond overlap populations were obtained by Mulliken population analysis¹². The square-planar geometry around rhodium is maintained for these systems and coordinate system is given in Fig. 1.

TABLE 1—PARAMETERS USED IN CNDO/2 CALCULATIONS

Atom	Orbital exponent	Beta	Mulliken's electro-negativity	Subshell Mulliken's electronegativity
Rh	$5s$	1.360	-19.357	6.107 4
	$5p$	1.360	-19.357	1.446 3
	$4d$	2.775	-21.127	7.759 0
Cl	$3s$	2.033	-22.330	21.591 0
	$3p$	2.033	-22.330	8.708 0
S	$3s$	1.817	-18.150	17.650 0
	$3p$	1.817	-18.150	6.689 0
P	$3s$	1.600	-15.070	14.033 0
	$3p$	1.600	-15.070	5.464 0
O	$2s$	2.275	-31.000	25.390 2
	$2p$	2.275	-31.000	9.111 0
N	$2s$	1.950	-25.000	19.316 0
	$2p$	1.950	-25.000	7.275 0
C	$2s$	1.625	-21.000	14.051 0
	$2p$	1.625	-21.000	5.572 0
H	$1s$	1.200	-09.000	7.176 1

Fig. 1. Coordinate system for *trans*-[Rh(L)(Cl)PH₃)₂] [L = SO, SO₂]; Z axis is out of the plane

Interatomic distances and bond angles employed in the calculations were approximated on the basis of X-ray diffraction studies for iridium sulphur monoxide complex⁸ and the rhodium sulphur dioxide complexes^{13,14}: for [Rh(SO)Cl(PH₃)₂], Rh-S = 2.23 Å, S-O = 1.32 Å, Rh-Cl = 2.38 Å, Rh-P = 2.33 Å and angle Rh-S-O = 130°; for [Rh(SO₂)Cl(PH₃)₂], Rh-S = 2.096 Å, S-O = 1.44 Å, Rh-Cl = 2.36 Å, Rh-P = 2.33 Å and angle Rh-S-O = 122.8°. The PH₃ has P-H bonds of 1.4 Å and H-P-H angle 109.5°. All calculations were performed using the QCPE 474 Program¹⁵ implemented on ICIM-6000 computer.

TABLE 2—UPPER-VALENCE MOLECULAR ORBITALS OF *trans* [Rh(SO)Cl(PH₃)₂]

Level	Energy eV	%Contributions			
		Rh	SO	Cl	PH ₃
7a" (LUMO)	0.238 7	37.4	12.2	4.9	45.5
6a" (HOMO)	-7.004 0	65.9	28.6	—	5.3
16a'	-9.543 6	48.6	44.7	3.3	3.4
15a'	-10.218 0	71.5	16.9	5.2	6.4
14a'	-10.352 3	86.5	4.0	4.0	5.5
13a'	-10.553 5	69.1	21.2	5.0	4.7

Results and Discussion

The results of CNDO/2 molecular orbital calculations are presented in Table 2 for the upper-valence molecular orbitals of *trans*-[Rh(SO)Cl(PH₃)₂]. The discussion is focussed on those orbitals primarily responsible for Rh-S-O bonding. One can envision the formation of 6a" (H.O.M.O.) as being derived from the interactions of 5p_z and 4d_{yz} orbitals of rhodium with 3π* orbital of SO. This 6a" molecular orbital is Rh-S bonding and has 65.9% Rh character of which 89% is Rhd. I feel that it is this 6a" component that makes the major contribution to the Rh-SO π-bond. The unoccupied orbital of lowest energy (L.U.M.O.) can be well derived as π* orbital (7a") which consists of combination between 5p_z and 4d_{yz} on the rhodium antibonding with 3π* orbital of SO and with lone-pairs of the PH₃ ligands. The 16a' molecular orbital is derived from the interaction between 4d_{xy} on the rhodium antibonding with respect to the 7σ orbital on SO. The filled 16a' orbital has 48.6% Rh

character of which 100% is Rhd. The 13a', 14a' and 15a' molecular orbitals are localised on Cl-Rh-S-O and have more than 69% Rh character.

TABLE 3—BOND STRENGTHS (WIBERG INDICES) FOR *trans*-[Rh(L)Cl(PH₃)₂] (L = SO, SO₂)

Bond	[Rh(SO)Cl(PH ₃) ₂]	[Rh(SO ₂)Cl(PH ₃) ₂]
Rh-S	1.239 1	1.240 2
σ	0.763 8	0.728 4
π	0.475 3	0.511 8
Rh(s)-S	0.189 5	0.184 5
Rh(p)-S	0.546 3	0.537 3
Rh(d)-S	0.503 3	0.537 5
S-O	1.499 2	1.190 9
σ	0.986 6	0.948 8
π	0.512 6	0.242 1
Rh-Cl	1.056 5	1.085 7
σ	0.767 5	4.775 4
π	0.289 0	0.310 3

Bond strength results (as measured by Wiberg indices¹⁶) are listed in Table 3. The results indicate that the SO and SO₂ ligands act as a σ-donor by donating electrons to the rhodium and also as a π-acceptor by accepting electrons from the rhodium. The values of the Rh-S Wiberg indices are same for both the complexes. The Rh-S σ-bond components for Rh-SO complex [Rh(s)-S = 0.1895, Rh(pσ)-S = 0.3698, Rh(dσ)-S = 0.2045] is greater than the Rh-S σ-bond components for Rh-SO₂ complex [Rh(s)-S = 0.1845, Rh(pr)-S = 0.3517, Rh(dσ)-S = 0.1922] whereas the Rh-S π-bond components for Rh-SO complex [Rh(ππ)-S = 0.1765, Rh(dπ)-S = 0.2989] is smaller than the Rh-S π-bond components for Rh-SO₂ complex [Rh(ππ)-S = 0.1665, Rh(dπ)-S = 0.3453]. The largest difference between the components of the Rh-S bonds in these complexes occurs with the Rh(dπ)-S components. These results suggest that the SO ligand is a better σ-donor and a poor π-acceptor than the SO₂.

σ-Donation tends to raise the W_{S-O}, since electrons are removed from antibonding σ-orbital while π-backbonding tends to decrease the W_{S-O} because the electrons enter into the antibonding π-orbital. The increasing value of S-O Wiberg indices in sulphur monoxide complex above sulphur dioxide complex confirms the better σ-donor and poor π-acceptor abilities of the SO ligand. The σ-

bond and π -bond fractional bond indices for S–O bond are greater in sulphur monoxide complex than in sulphur dioxide complex.

TABLE 4—ORBITAL CHARGES AND GROSS ATOMIC CHARGES FOR *trans*-(Rh[SO]Cl(PH₃)₂) (L = SO, SO₂)

System	Orbital charges		Atomic charges	
[Rh(SO)Cl(PH ₃) ₂]	Rh		Rh = -0.823 7	
	5s	0.688 6	3s	1.8158
	5p	1.596 5	3p	5.4232
	4d	7.358 6		
	S		O	
	3s	1.563 5	2s	1.7183
	3p	2s	4.6410	
(Rh(SO ₂)Cl(PH ₃) ₂)	Rh		Rh = -0.862 3	
	5s	0.684 4	3s	1.810 1
	5p	1.559 6	3p	5.399 8
	4d	7.618 3		
	S		O	
	3s	1.383 5	2s	1.772 7
	3p	2p	4.755 3	

The changes in the σ -bonding and π -bonding due to the substitution of a SO ligand for a SO₂ ligand with a relatively large σ -bond and small π -bond components result in a decreases in the *trans*-Rh–Cl σ -bond and π -bond components and hence, the *trans*-Rh–Cl bond weakened for sulphur monoxide complex.

Orbital charges and gross atomic charges are presented in Table 4. Positive charges of 0.0867 and 0.0219 on SO and SO₂ ligands respectively, suggest that SO ligand is a better electron-donor to the central rhodium atom than the SO₂ ligand. The trend in SO and SO₂ charges is the same as the

trend of S–O Wiberg indices. The chloro ligand is a better electron-remover from the rhodium in sulphur monoxide complex than that in sulphur dioxide complex.

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